

Studies in the Chemistry of Metal Iodides. Part I. Thermal Decomposition of Strontium Iodide

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Data obtained by thermogravimetric analysis of anhydrous and hexahydrated strontium iodide and those by D.T.A. of $SrI_2 \cdot 6H_2O$ are reported.

In the fissioning of uranium by thermal neutrons, iodine is one of the important fission products with a total yield of about 27% for the different isotopes. Being a volatile substance even at relatively low temperatures, it is important to systematically study (i) its reactions with other materials, particularly the high-yield fission products, and (ii) the thermal stability of iodides formed.

As little work has been done on these iodides, the thermal decomposition in air of the hexahydrated and anhydrous strontium iodide is reported in this communication. Gay-Lussac¹ observed that the iodide could be melted without decomposition in absence of air, but in its presence it was partially decomposed. Etard² found the transition temperature for the hexahydrate to dihydrate conversion as 90°.

EXPERIMENTAL

The thermal decomposition of strontium iodide hexahydrate was studied with a Stanton recording thermobalance of 1 mg. sensitivity and also by differential thermal analysis. The starting material used was E. Merck's $SrI_2 \cdot 6H_2O$.

The compound started dehydrating at about 90° and various decomposition steps were observed (Table I, Fig. 1).

TABLE I

Decomp. step.	Starting temp.	Ending temp.	% Loss on basis of original.	Reaction centres.
1	90°	180°	8°	$SrI_2 \cdot 6H_2O \rightarrow SrI_2 \cdot 4H_2O + 2H_2O$
2	180°	275°	20°	$\rightarrow SrI_2 \cdot H_2O$
3	280°	370°	*24°	$\rightarrow SrI_2 \rightarrow Sr_5(IO_6)_2$
4	370°	525°	60°	
5	900°	980°	76°	$\rightarrow SrO$

*There is no clearly demarcated anhydrous stage.

1. *Ann. chim. phys.*, 1814, *i*, 91, 5.

2. *Ibid.*, 1894, *vii*, 2, 528.

The strontium oxide, thus obtained at the end of the decomposition, did not remain as the oxide, but soon changed into the hydroxide $\text{Sr}(\text{OH})_2$ in the atmosphere, as was seen from (i) the gain in weight on keeping [18.2% gain in weight as observed was required for the conversion $\text{SrO} \rightarrow \text{Sr}(\text{OH})_2$], (ii) condensation of water on the cooler parts of the test-tube on heating the residue kept in air for some time, and (iii) the X-ray pattern of the residue which does not correspond to the SrO pattern.

FIG. 1. Strontium iodide hexahydrate.
Heating rate = $4^\circ/\text{min.} (^\circ\text{C})$.

The intermediate compound obtained at about 530° , which remained stable up to 900° , was analysed. From the percentage composition (Table II) and the percentage losses obtained on heating, it is assigned the formula $\text{Sr}_3(\text{IO}_6)_2$; the corresponding barium salt is known³.

The X-ray powder pattern of this intermediate compound is listed in Table III.

TABLE II

	Theoretical.	Obtained.
%Composition:		
Strontium	49.55	48.0
Iodate	50.45	51.5
% Loss from $\text{SrI}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ to form intermediate compound	60.66	60.0
% Loss to form SrO from intermediate compound	41.75	40.0

3. Sagiura and Cross, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1879, 35, 11^a.

TABLE III

$d.$	HI_{σ}	$d.$	HI_{σ}
3.51 Å	10	2.040 Å	19
3.02	23	1.960	6
2.30	100	1.895	7
2.46	0	1.884	15
2.07	20	1.058	16

FIG. 2. Differential thermal analysis of strontium iodide hexahydrate.

Fig. 3. Thermogravimetric analysis of anhydrous SrI_2 .

The thermal decomposition of $\text{SrI}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ was also studied by differential thermal analysis (Fig. 2). Three prominent endothermic peaks were obtained, corresponding to the three dehydration steps observed in thermogravimetric analysis. A fourth endothermic peak was obtained, which corresponded to the formation temperature of the intermediate compound. The last peak was exothermic and corresponded to the decomposition of the periodate to the oxide.

$\text{SrI}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ was also heated in vacuum up to 700° and found to furnish the anhydrous iodide. This anhydrous iodide was heated in air on the thermobalance (Fig. 3). Decomposition began at 480° and proceeded at a slower rate than in the case of the hydrate. It was complete only at about 880° , when 48% loss was recorded, corresponding to the formation of the periodate. Further decomposition took place at about 950° with a further loss of 21%, resulting finally in the oxide.

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